

VANISHING POINT DETECTION BASED ON THE FUSION OF LIDAR AND IMAGE DATA

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Abstract—Despite the great progress that has been done in vanishing point-based methods for road detection using visual information the results are still vulnerable to external light conditions. For that reason, the fusion of LIDAR data, alongside images can be used for a more reliable result. LIDAR data may lack illumination information but are less susceptible to light conditions. The main contribution of this paper is the use of LIDAR data to create a mask that will restrict the area of the image that could eventually be the road. More specifically, we are using LIDAR data to detect the points of the ground. By contracting an Octree, we find the best-fitting plane of each leaf and by performing clustering we estimate the ground. Next, we are mapping the points of the road to the image to create a mask for the image processing step. We extract the texture orientation using Gabor Filter and thereafter the vanishing point. The proposed approach has been implemented and tested with over 1000 images of different road scenes in the KITTI dataset. The experimental results demonstrate that this training-free approach can detect horizon and vanishing point very accurately and robustly, while achieving promising performance.

Index Terms—Vanishing point detection, LiDAR Processing, Image Processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Road detection remains a challenging issue due to the variety of road surfaces, weather, and lighting conditions. There are multiple image-based approaches that try to handle the problem of road segmentation with different non-learning approaches. According to [1] a significant number of researchers are handling the problem by analyzing the image texture and trying to extract specific characteristics of the road such as boundaries, curbs, mark lines or identify the differences of the texture between surfaces of the road and the rest of the image. Another approach is to detect the road based on similarity criteria, edges and color structure, of the given image and a database of known surfaces [2]. Significant impact on the road segmentation problem have methods that are searching for the vanishing point and seem to perform well even on unconstructed roads, were curbs or lane marks are occluded, because they are based on global characteristics of the road surface [3]–[6]. As we have mentioned features of the road are sometimes occluded and adding to that unknown lighting conditions makes the problem even more challenging to be handled solely by image-based methods. To overcome these issues many studies, have introduced LIDAR information. Because LIDAR is an active scanning sensor is unaffected by ambient light variations

and performs well in low light conditions. However road segmentation based only on LIDAR is not always feasible because lane marks do not have a 3D structure, LIDAR is mainly used in object detection or curb detection [7]. In order to exploit image and LIDAR information fusion techniques have been proposed [8]–[10].

In this paper, we present a geometric approach in order to fuse the two different data sources and improve the result of the vanishing point-based road detection methods. The contribution of this paper is that it adds a preprocessing step on the image analysis problem in order to restrict the points that should take part in the voting procedure for the vanishing point. More specifically we detect the ground from LIDAR data and by mapping its point to the image plane a constrain for the road segmentation is formed. In that way, we create a more robust result to external illumination and occlusions that could be caused by other vehicles or obstacles.

II. RELATED WORK

Multiple non-learning methods for road detection are based on edge detection in order to find boundaries or lane markings. Lines can be detected using Hough transform [11], Color cue or Spline models [12]. These methods are based on the assumption that roads belong to homogeneous surfaces as well-paved roads and they are looking for distinctive road cues. While texture-based methods estimate the local orientation of the pixels of the image and then choose the vanishing point based on the global texture characteristics [3]–[6], [13]. By finding the vanishing point they have a strong constraint for the segmentation process of the road area. The main workflow of these baseline methods could be summarized in three steps:

1) *Estimate the texture orientation for every pixel of the image:* in the majority of the papers, it is implemented with Gabor Filter Banks. 2D Gabor filters are proven [14] to describe well the 2D receptive-field profiles of simple cells in the mammalian visual cortex and optimize the general uncertainty relations for joint 2D-spatial-2D-spectral information resolution.

2) *Establish a voting strategy and select a pixel, the vanishing-point, where texture orientations converge to:* Different voting procedures have been proposed [3]–[6]. In [4] Rasmussen proposed a hard-voting strategy in which the pixels that are able to vote are the pixels below the vanishing-point candidate regardless of their relative distance. This approach was favoring the pixel higher in the image, that tent to have more voting pixels. To overcome this issue a soft-voting scheme was proposed in [3] where the distance between

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the voter and the candidate vanishing-point is considered. The soft-voting scheme seems to outperform the hard-voting strategy.

3) *Find road boundaries using as start the vanishing point*: Line detection techniques such as Hough transform have been widely used [5], [15]. Other approaches are based on the percentage of consistency that the selected border has with the estimated texture orientation [3], [16] and the color difference between the two region that the border indicates. Vanishing points can be also estimated based on stereo cameras. As proposed on [13] a stereo camera is used to generate u- and v-disparity maps of road image, from which the horizon and the ground can be extracted. These features are used as constraint to robustly locate the vanishing point. After locating the vanishing point, it handles the problem of the border detection of the road as a Dijkstra minimum-cost map. Both disparity and gradient of a gray scale image are used to calculate the cost between two neighbor pixels. In [17] a stereo vision-based method uses a recognition algorithm driven by a statistical model of the 3D road lane projected in both stereoscopic images. After the implementation of the training stage of the model, parameters of the 3D lane, such as the width, horizontal and vertical curvature, roll, pitch, and yaw angles, are been calculated.

Although learning approaches are beyond the scope of this paper, image segmentation methods with the use of deep convolutional neural networks (DCNN) with methods as [18] achieve very good performance. The method that seems to have the best results and is currently top of the publicly accessible benchmark KITTI is presented in [9]. With the use of both LIDAR and image, it proposes a novel approach in order to effectively project LIDAR features to visual features through a cascaded fusion structure and subsequently segment the road surface of the image.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section III presents the ground estimation from LIDAR data. Section IV details the point projection from LIDAR to the image plane. In Section V we describe the texture orientation estimation using Gabor Filters. Section VI details the voting scheme. Results and conclusions are presented in Section VII and Section VIII respectively.

III. GROUND ESTIMATION

An Octree data structure that takes as input the cloud $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$ taken from the LIDAR, aims to rapidly cluster it in small surface patches $R = \{r_1, r_2 \dots, r_m\}$. The terminal condition for the subdivision of the 3D space is chosen to be the minimum voxel size d_{min} , which empirically is set to be $0.3 m$. The ground can be best characterized by a plane so for every surface patch the corresponding best-fitting plane is calculated with the use of a Random Sample and Consensus (RANSAC) algorithm. The main concept of a RANSAC algorithm is that it selects randomly three points and calculates the parameters of the corresponding plane. Then it detects all points of the original cloud belonging to the calculated plane, according to a given

threshold. Afterward, it repeats these procedures N times and it keeps the optimal solution.

The calculated plane of every surface patch is now represented by its center and its normal vector. These features, centers $C = \{c_1, c_2 \dots, c_m\}$ and their corresponding normal vectors $N = \{n_1, n_2 \dots, n_m\}$, would be the input of a region growing algorithm, which is implemented with the publicly available Point Cloud Library PCL [19]. The constraints that the algorithm takes as inputs are an angle threshold and a curvature threshold.

1) *Angle Threshold*: The angle threshold is a constraint for the deviation between the norms of two points. If n_1, n_2 their normal vectors the deviation between them is given by $\cos^{-1}(n_1 \bullet n_2)$.

2) *Curvature Threshold*: The curvature threshold is a constraint for the deviation between their curvature values. The curvature value for a point c_i is estimated with an analysis of the eigenvectors and eigenvalues of a covariance matrix created in a k -nearest neighborhood of the query point. The covariance matrix $Cov \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is defined [20] by:

$$Cov = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (c_i - \bar{c}) \cdot (c_i - \bar{c})^T, Cov \cdot \vec{v}_j = \lambda_j \cdot \vec{v}_j, j \in 1, 2, 3 \quad (1)$$

where \bar{c} represent the 3D centroid of the neighborhood and the curvature value is defined by:

$$\frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3}, \text{ where } \lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \lambda_3 \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2)$$

The angle threshold is set to 2 degrees and the curvature threshold to 0.5.

Thereby, the output of this algorithm is a set of clusters, where each cluster is a set of points belonging to the same surface. We keep the two clusters with the maximum number of points and as the ground is selected the one that its center has the smallest absolute value of y coordinate. The LIDAR coordinate system is defined as x = forward, y = left, z = up. Consequently by tacking the minimum $|y|$ value we keep the cluster in front of the vehicle. Clusters with less than 100 points are being discarded. Finally, a RANSAC algorithm is performed to the selected cluster with a threshold of $15cm$ to remove outliers.

IV. POINT PROJECTION

In order to project the point of the LIDAR to the image plane, we are using the calibration data provided by the KITTI benchmark. The LIDAR that is used in the benchmark, is the Velodyne HDL-64E S2 and each point is stored with its (x, y, z) coordinate and an additional reflectance value (r). While the number of points per scan is not constant, on average each file/frame has $\sim 120,000$ 3D points and reflectance values [21]. The rigid body transformation

Fig. 1. Examples of the mask that is created from ground detection. The black circles indicate the detected ground points.

from Velodyne coordinates to camera coordinates are given in detail at [21] and are expressed by:

$$T_{velo}^{cam} = \begin{pmatrix} R_{velo}^{cam} & t_{velo}^{cam} \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where $R_{velo}^{cam} \in R^{3 \times 3}$ is the rotation matrix and $t_{velo}^{cam} \in R^{1 \times 3}$ the translation vector from Velodyne to the camera coordinate system. The projection of a 3D point $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, z, 1)^T$ in the LIDAR coordinates system gets projected to a point in the camera plane $\mathbf{y} = (u, v, 1)^T$ according to:

$$\mathbf{y} = T_{velo}^{cam} \mathbf{x} \quad (4)$$

And then in the rectified (rotated) camera coordinates of \mathbf{y} are given by

$$\mathbf{y}_{rec} = T_{rec} \mathbf{y} \quad (5)$$

where T_{rec} is the rectification matrix.

Having the ground points from LIDAR data the aforementioned transformation is applied and a sparse mask is created to the part of the image where the ground is located. In order to have a more dense result a 10-pixel radius circle is assigned at each point of the ground, and thus we have the result as shown in Fig. 1. The mask will be used as a restriction to the points that will vote for the vanishing point.

V. TEXTURE ORIENTATION

The usage of Gabor filters is a well-known technic that has been used by many researchers for various image processing tasks because their properties are particularly useful for texture analysis because of the 2D spectral specificity of

texture as well as its variation with 2D spatial position. These wavelets are also used for motion detection, stereoscopic vision, and many sorts of visual pattern recognition such as face recognition [22]. The 2D Gabor function is thus a product of an elliptical Gaussian and a complex plane wave and can be defined [23] in the following form:

$$G_{\omega, \theta}(x, y) = \exp\left(-\frac{x'^2 + \gamma^2 y'^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \exp(j\omega x' + \text{phase}) \quad (6)$$

$$x' = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta \quad (7)$$

$$y' = -x \sin \theta + y \cos \theta \quad (8)$$

The radius frequency of the complex plane wave is represented by ω ; θ is the orientation of the wavelet in radian; σ is the standard deviation of the Gaussian function; γ is the aspect ratio. In this paper, we compute the real part and the imaginary part separately. Afterward, we compute the convolution of the original grayscale images with both the real and imaginary parts of the Gabor kernel. The imaginary and the real part of the Gabor kernel are formulated as follows:

$$\text{Im}(G_{\omega, \theta}(x, y)) = \exp\left(-\frac{x'^2 + \gamma^2 y'^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \sin(j\omega x') \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Re}(G_{\omega, \theta}(x, y)) = \exp\left(-\frac{x'^2 + \gamma^2 y'^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \cos(j\omega x') \quad (10)$$

The Family of Gabor Kernels that are applied to the image have $n = 36$ different orientations (180 divided by 5) and for every orientation, we consider 5 different scales ($\omega = 2.1 \times 2^s$ ($s = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4$)). The same parameters have also been used in [5], [23]. In order to get the texture orientation at each pixel, we take the norm of the complex response of the real and imaginary part of the Gabor filter for each filter applied. The orientation that will be selected is the one that has the average maximum response for the 5 different scales. In Fig. 2 the result of the estimation of texture orientation is presented.

VI. VOTING

Having an estimation of the texture orientation we are voting for the selection of the vanishing-point. Our approach uses a soft-voting [3] scheme, but we take into consideration only pixels that belong to the ground.

$$\text{Vote}(P, V) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1 + [\gamma d(P, V)]^2} & \text{if } \gamma \leq \frac{5}{1 + 2d(P, V)} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 2. Examples of the texture orientation estimation for the ground region. The direction of the red lines indicates the texture orientation at the starting pixel of the lines.

Fig. 3. Examples of the vanishing point localization. The blue circle indicates its place.

V stands for the vanishing-point candidate, while P is the Voter; γ is the angle in degrees between the direction PV and the estimation of the texture orientation at pixel P ; the $d(P, V)$ is the distance between P and V divided by the diagonal length of the image. For every vanishing-point candidate, the pixels that can vote should belong to the ground and be below it and within a distance of $0.35 * Y$, where Y is the length of the image diagonal. Y is an empirical parameter as it is proposed in [3].

VII. RESULTS

The localization of the vanishing point with our method is tested on 1000 images on the KITTI datasheet on different cases. The original images were cropped and are normalized

to the same size. More specifically, the top 100 rows and 300 columns from each side were removed. The images that did not had noticeable road vanishing points were removed from the validation set. To assess its performance we had to manually label the ground-truth vanishing point locations. Five researchers were requested to indicate the vanishing point after they were trained on the concept of it. To have an unbiased result of the subjectivity of each individual in the localization of the vanishing point, a median filter is applied to the human results.

Around the ground truth, we have taken a circle with a 30-pixel radius. The vanishing points that were within this radius were considered to be valid. About 90% of them were within the manual labeled circle, while 65% of images have got errors of less than or equal to 10 pixels. Fig. 3 shows same successful results.

Our vanishing point estimation method is robust to non-homogeneous textures such as bushes and trees which are very challenging for other methods [3], [24]. They do not belong to the ground and so they are excluded from the voting procedure. In case of heavy traffic, there is not enough voting region and as a consequence, the algorithm fails. However, when the occlusion caused by other vehicles does not occupy a large part of the image our methods find successfully the vanishing point unaffected by other vehicles.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we propose a fusion technique for the LIDAR and camera sensor. The ground detection from LIDAR being used as a constraint for the image processing step make the result more robust to external light condition and occlusions. Our method may have good results on many different scenes and gives a good estimation of the place of the vanishing point, although the general road detection problem is a more complicated issue that needs more cues to be considered successful. As future work is to use geometric characteristics from both sensors and by taking advantage of the progress that has been done in DNN to have more robust and generic results.

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